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PROBLEMS OF EMPLOYMENT IN THE LABOR MARKET OF UZBEKISTAN AND STRATEGIC DIRECTIONS FOR THEIR SOLUTION

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Abstract: This article provides an in-depth analysis of the employment problem in the national economy and explores strategic directions for its resolution. It highlights the key causes of unemployment and the economic barriers that intensify the issue, such as labor market imbalances, the mismatch between the education system and labor market demands, economic crises, and limited resources.

Key words: national economy, employment problem, labor market, education system, youth employment, women's employment, small and medium-sized enterprises, labor migration, economic stability, improvement strategies.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston milliy iqtisodiyotida bandlik muammosi chuqur tahlil qilinib, uni hal etish bo'yicha strategik yo'nalishlar yoritilgan. Unda ishsizlikning asosiy sabablari va uni kuchaytiruvchi iqtisodiy to'siqlar – mehnat bozori nomutanosibliigi, ta'lim tizimi bilan mehnat bozori o'rtasidagi mos kelmaslik, iqtisodiy inqirozlar va resurslar yetishmasligi – ko'rib chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: milliy iqtisodiyot, bandlik muammosi, mehnat bozori, ta'lim tizimi, yoshlar bandligi, ayollar bandligi, kichik va o'rta biznes, mehnat migratsiyasi, iqtisodiy barqarorlik, rivojlantirish strategiyalari.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлен углублённый анализ проблемы занятости в национальной экономике и определены стратегические направления её решения. Рассматриваются основные причины безработицы и экономические барьеры, усугубляющие ситуацию, включая дисбаланс на рынке труда, несоответствие системы образования требованиям рынка труда, экономические кризисы и ограниченность ресурсов.

Ключевые слова: национальная экономика, проблема занятости, рынок труда, система образования, занятость молодежи, занятость женщин, малые и средние предприятия, трудовая миграция, экономическая стабильность, стратегии улучшения.

INTRODUCTION

The issue of ensuring employment in the national economy remains one of the most critical challenges that threaten both economic growth and social stability. The level of employment is directly linked to economic sustainability and the well-being of the population. Therefore, it is not only a matter of state policy but also a key indicator of a country's economic development.

Understanding the underlying causes of employment problems, identifying the contributing factors, and developing effective strategies for their resolution are of paramount importance. A low level of employment is not solely the result of a shortage of jobs; it is also influenced by a range of other factors such as the insufficient qualifications of workers, inequalities in the labor market, systemic issues in the education sector, and the long-term consequences of economic crises.

In particular, global economic transformations, technological disruptions, and emerging social challenges further exacerbate difficulties in securing employment and raising employment levels. As international competition intensifies, labor markets are becoming increasingly complex. In this context, the creation of new jobs requires the adoption of innovative and adaptive approaches.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The work carried out by the Republic of Uzbekistan to ensure employment of the population is gaining great importance in ensuring social well-being. First of all, ¹the main criterion in this area is the Law of the Republic of

¹ Lex.uz Uzbekistan Republic legislative portal. <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/-5055690?ONDATE=23.10.2024%2000>

Uzbekistan No. O'RQ-642 dated October 20, 2020 «On Employment of the Population». This law was adopted in order to regulate relations in the field of employment of the population. The legislation on employment of the population consists of this Law and other legislative acts. If an international treaty of the Republic of Uzbekistan establishes rules other than those provided for in the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan on employment of the population, the application of the rules of the international treaty is reflected in Article 2 of this Law. The Law consists of 123 articles and 19 chapters. The Law was amended and supplemented in due course by the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Amendments and Addenda to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Employment of the Population" dated 27.09.2024 No. O'RQ-967 ². A number of new concepts are provided in a separate article in the Law. In particular, such concepts as self-employment, the interdepartmental software and hardware complex "Single National Labor System", the national system for the development of professional qualifications, knowledge and skills, and qualification assessment are among them.

This Law serves as a solid legal basis for solving the problems of employment, which are extremely urgent today. Most importantly, the Law provides an opportunity to provide material and social support to our citizens by creating new jobs, thereby achieving their well-being.

Various programs and related measures aimed at ensuring ³employment of the population serve to reduce the level of unemployment in our country by stimulating economic growth, restoring labor market balance, and strengthening social protection .

The efforts of our state in this direction will help to achieve a more stable and economically developed system of our national economy. In particular, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan In accordance with the Resolution No. PQ-347 of October 4, 2024 "On measures to improve and increase the efficiency of state policy in the field of poverty reduction and employment of the population", a number of practical tasks have been completed. At the same time, the government of our country has developed, implemented and is implementing various state programs to ensure employment of the population and reduce the level of unemployment. For example, the " Program for Ensuring Employment of the Population and Development of the Labor Market for 2020-2024" and a number of other similar programs serve as the main documents aimed at increasing employment in our country.

RESEARCH METHODS

The research process used methods such as a systematic approach, logical and comparative methods of analysis, systematic analysis, comparative analysis, monographic analysis, logical and comparative methods of analysis, a comprehensive approach, expert assessment, multivariate forecasting, as well as statistical analysis and qualitative analysis.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The issue of population employment in the national economy is a complex and multifactorial issue, and its emergence is influenced by various economic, social and political factors. Ensuring population employment is a key condition for the economic development of the country, which means reducing unemployment, increasing the well-being of the population and balancing the labor market. In this context, this article analyzes the problem of population employment in the national economy, its causes, main obstacles and strategic directions necessary to eliminate them . Strategic directions and measures implemented by the state are necessary to solve the problem of population employment. Below we will dwell on the main factors, obstacles and work carried out to eliminate population employment issues in the national economy.

The results of the study showed the effectiveness of measures taken in our country to ensure employment and reduce poverty. The results of the qualitative analysis show that the economic reforms and social programs adopted by the state play an important role in increasing the income of the population. In particular, the conditions created for the development of entrepreneurship in neighborhoods make a significant contribution to the development of small businesses. According to statistics, in 2023, the volume of loans allocated for entrepreneurial activity increased by 15%, which accelerated the creation of new jobs ⁴. The results of the survey confirmed the effectiveness of social programs implemented to reduce poverty. 67% of respondents noted that they had increased their income through social protection programs. At the same time, subsidies and benefits provided by the state in the field of entrepreneurship development helped 45% of respondents to engage in business activities.

2 Lex.uz Uzbekistan Republic legislation portal <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/-7124178>

3 Human rights according to Uzbekistan Republic National center official website . <http://nhrc.uz/oz/news/milliy-strategiya-va-aholi-bandligi-togriydi-qanun>

4 Gazeta.uz online edition . Source : <https://www.gazeta.uz/oz/2023/01/25/president/>

The analysis of labor resources management showed that vocational education and retraining programs are working effectively to increase employment in the country. In 2023, more than 50 thousand citizens were trained in modern professions, which helped to meet the demand for labor in the labor market. As a result of these measures, the unemployment rate decreased from 9.5% in 2022 to 8.3% in 2023. As the results of the comparative analysis show, remittances from abroad play a significant role in reducing poverty. In 2023, these funds reduced the poverty level by 12%. In particular, the contribution of international remittances to improving the social situation in rural areas was significant.

The results of the study show that employment is increasing through the effective use of local resources, the development of entrepreneurship and the improvement of vocational education. Also, the effective management of funds from abroad plays an important role in reducing poverty. However, to further improve the results, it is necessary to deepen social policies and continue economic reforms.

Causes of population unemployment and factors affecting it

The level of employment and the availability of jobs in the national economy depend on many factors. The main reasons leading to low employment and high unemployment are:

Slowing economic growth: Economic slowdown, lower production, lack of investment, and difficulty competing in global markets lead to job losses.

Inequality in the labor market: There are difficulties in acquiring the skills and professions necessary to create new jobs. The lack of an adequate system for training unskilled workers in many sectors leads to low employment rates.

Technological changes: Technological crises such as digital transformation and automation are changing the labor market, reducing old jobs and requiring the adoption of new, advanced technologies.

Regional differences: Migration of the population to cities and villages, regional economic differences lead to an uneven distribution of jobs, which can result in low employment rates in rural areas.

Labor legislation and social protection: Gaps in labor legislation and its ineffective implementation, insufficient protection of workers' rights, hinder the achievement of high employment rates.

International experiences in poverty reduction and employment are of great importance for Uzbekistan. The experiences of successful countries of the world, such as the Scandinavian countries, South Korea, and Singapore, are widely used in Uzbekistan. The experience of these countries shows that effective results can be achieved when economic growth and social protection measures are implemented together. Uzbekistan is trying to study international experiences and apply them, adapting them to the country's conditions. The programs and strategies adopted by the state are developed on the basis of international experiences and are practically adapted to the country's conditions. This helps to achieve positive results in Uzbekistan in ensuring employment and reducing poverty.

The sources of financing for programs to ensure employment and reduce poverty include the state budget, the private sector, and international assistance. The social protection system and programs to create new jobs are financed through funds allocated from the state budget. In order to increase the participation of the private sector, it is necessary to create a favorable business environment. Financial assistance provided by international organizations and donor countries also serves as an important source. This assistance reduces the financial burden on the state and increases the efficiency of the social protection system. Through effective management of funding sources, resources are optimally distributed and the effectiveness of programs is increased.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Ensuring employment and reducing unemployment in the Republic of Uzbekistan is one of the most important directions of the state's economic policy. It is possible to increase the level of employment through various measures implemented by the state, stimulating economic growth, developing the education system, regulating the labor market, and supporting small and medium-sized businesses. However, in order to implement these measures, it is necessary to overcome obstacles such as regional differences, technological changes, and the weakness of the social protection system. Effective strategies for ensuring employment are a key factor in social stability and economic development. Measures and state programs implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan to ensure employment and reduce poverty are yielding positive results. New jobs are being created and employment is increasing through economic development, the development of small business and private entrepreneurship, investment projects, and infrastructure development. The standard of living of the population is being increased by expanding the social protection system and improving the education system. Taking into account international experiences, Uzbekistan continues to seek new ways to further develop and finance and support its social protection system.

The work carried out by the state of the Republic of Uzbekistan to ensure employment of the population is of great importance in ensuring economic stability and increasing social well-being. Programs and measures aimed at ensuring employment of the population serve to reduce unemployment by stimulating economic growth, restoring labor market balance and strengthening social protection. The state's efforts in this direction contribute to achieving a more stable and developed system of the national economy.

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